

IMPACT OF EXCHANGE RATE VOLATILITY ON ECONOMIC GROWTH: A CASE STUDY OF A SMALL OPEN ECONOMY

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Abstract

The paper examined the impact of exchange rate volatility on the economic growth in Nigeria. Using annual time series data from 1980 to 2024, and Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) methodology the result of the unit root test revealed that Gross Domestic Product growth rate, foreign direct investment and exchange rate were stationary at level, while trade openness, Inflation Rate, and Interest rate are Stationary at first difference. The ARDL estimation, the Bounds Test shows that there is a long run cointegrating relationship between the dependent and independent variables, both in the short run and long run. The ARDL estimations revealed that foreign direct investment, interest rate, and trade openness had a positive and significant impact on the economic growth in Nigeria, while exchange rate and inflation rate impacted negatively and insignificantly on the economic growth in Nigeria during the period under review. The Granger causality test shows that unidirectional relationship runs between interest rate and gross domestic product growth rate, while no causality runs between the following variables; exchange rate and GDP growth rate, inflation rate and GDP growth rate, foreign direct investment and GDP growth rate, as well as trade openness and GDP growth rate. In other words, Exchange rate does not Granger Cause GDP, also GDP does not Granger Cause Exchange rate. Based on the findings, the paper recommends the need for the Central Bank of Nigeria and other relevant stakeholders to embark on appropriate monetary policy aimed at addressing the challenges of high inflation rate as such can boost consumers' purchasing power.

Keywords: Exchange Rate, GDP Growth Rate and Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian economy has been visibly distressed in the different phases of exchange rate management (ERM); each coming with its own, possible problem. According to Idika (2024), frequent changes in foreign exchange policies caused by unstable political environment have prevented these policies from coming full circle. Exchange rate stability, which is essential for growth is influenced greatly by the appropriate policy mix by government in their quest to attain macroeconomic targets.

Fluctuations in exchange rate have powerful effects on imports and exports of the countries in question through relative prices of goods. Mordi (2023) posited that the Nigerian economy is highly dependent on imports for both consumption and production. According to World Bank (2020), many oil producing nations are exposed to variations in exchange rate due their large oil wealth. This variation which acts as tax on investment in trade goods production has adverse impact on growth especially on agricultural and manufacturing sectors. Ewa (2021) agreed that the exchange rate of the naira was relatively stable between 1970 and 1979 during the oil boom era and when agricultural produce accounted for more than 70% of the nation's Gross

Domestic Products (GDP). In 1986 when Federal government adopted Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP), the country moved from a pegged to a flexible regime where exchange rate was left completely to be determined by market forces but with monetary authorities intervening periodically in the foreign exchange market in order to attain some strategic objectives (Mordi, 2023). This inconsistency and lack of continuity in exchange rate policies aggravated the unstable nature of the naira rate (Gbosi, 2023). Benson and Victor (2021) and Aliyu (2021) noted that despite various efforts by the government to maintain a stable exchange rate, the naira has depreciated throughout the 80's to date. Gross National Product (GNP) was similarly affected. The combined effects of exchange rate variability on GDP and GNP, among others, resulted in the abysmal low level of per capita income of Nigerians.

The economic implication of this may not be clear to the ordinary citizens. What they invariably understand is that the Naira has lost reasonable proportion of its purchasing power. This is often reflected in the quantity of goods and services purchased by Naira (Okoroafor, 2023). Inconsistent management of the various exchange rate regimes adopted so far by the country to help check volatility appears to have jeopardized the overall macroeconomic policy objectives. According to Mordi (2023), once an exchange rate is not fixed it will be subject to variation, thereby making floating exchange rates more volatile. The degree of volatility and the extent of stability maintained are affected by economic fundamentals. Thus, strong economic fundamentals are meant to produce favourable economic environment. The naira exchange rate has been fluctuating since the introduction of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986. The Nigerian situation since SAP has mostly been characterized by increasing demand which outstripped supply, contributing generally to the continuous depreciation of the naira. The SAP was designed to deal with the underlying imbalances in the Nigerian economy following the collapse of international oil market. This phenomenon of excess demand for foreign exchange in relation to supply has contributed to the dwindling fortunes of the naira in all the foreign exchange markets. Also, weak production base and undiversified nature of the economy are among the factors that led to the depreciation of Naira.

The country's over dependency on oil as the main source of revenue resulted in negligence of non-oil exports for foreign exchange earnings in the early 1970s. The enormous foreign exchange earnings from crude oil exports encouraged the massive importation of finished goods and services.

The implication of over dependency on export of oil is that the economy is highly prone to external shocks to the extent that any crash in the oil price will lead to decline in foreign exchange earnings, and destabilizing effects on macroeconomic variables such as exchange rate, gross domestic product, interest rate, and inflation rate (Usman, 2022). In addition, given the high rate of naira depreciation and exchange rate dynamism in Nigeria, direct investment from other foreign countries into Nigeria has drop drastically over the years.

This will result to low trade performance both domestic and internationally. Depreciation of naira value coupled with Terrorism, armed robbery, kidnapping and other criminal activities as well as high inflation rate with other macroeconomic challenges confronting the nation are responsible for increasing cases of low trade performance in Nigeria.

No doubt, the above challenges will discourage foreigners or international investors to partner with Nigeria in the area of trade, and other related commercial transaction (Eze,2022). Given the drop in foreign direct investment and trade performance owing to exchange rate instability in Nigeria, foreign earning from foreign direct investment, foreign investment and international trade will reduce to the barest minimum. The challenge of naira depreciation will negatively affect the domestic production base of the country thereby leading to reduction in the exportation of goods and services to other nations. The economy will experience a relatively contraction in its revenue base, if not properly managed, it may lead to economic recession.

Given the above background discussion, this study seeks to examine the impact of exchange rate on the economic growth in Nigeria from 1980 to 2024. The rest of the paper is structured as follows; section two reviews the related literature on the subject matter with focus on the conceptual review, theoretical framework and empirical review. Section three presents the methodology of the study, while section four deals with findings, results and discussions. Finally, section five is conclusion and policy recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Exchange Rate

Exchange rate has been defined as the price of one currency in terms of another. It can be expressed in one of two ways: as units of domestic currency per unit of foreign currency ;or units of foreign currency per unit of domestic currency. For example, currently, Nigerian currency the Naira traded for about N1450 to a US dollar in the foreign exchange market (CBN,2024). However, since transactions are often carried out in national currencies, the former is generally applied for exchange. In addition, distinction is often made in the foreign exchange market between buying, selling and central rate. Exchange rate is the price of one country's currency in relation to another country (Madura, 2022). It is the required number of units of a currency that can buy another number of units of another currency (Eze,2022). The exchange rate dynamics is a prominent determinant of international trade with regard to export earnings generated there from. This concept has received much attention in the context of global imbalances in international trade.

A high exchange rate level lowers the receipts that exporters receive thereby decreasing export earnings. On the other hand, a low exchange rate level raises receipts that exporters receive thereby improving export earnings. A dynamic in the exchange rate impacts directly either positively or negatively on export earnings. Exchange rate fluctuations might impact negatively on exporters and trend economic growth by discouraging firms from undertaking investment, innovation and trade. It may also deter firms from entering the export market. Large fluctuations in foreign exchange rate impose adjustment costs on the economy as resources keep shifting between the tradable and non-tradable sectors. This could permanently shift resources to non-tradable sectors if firms are put off from export markets due to high foreign exchange rate fluctuations (Adamu, 2022).

If exchange rate movements are not fully anticipated, an increase in exchange rate fluctuations may lead risk-averse agents to reduce their international trading activities. The presumption of a negative nexus between exchange rate fluctuations and export earnings is an argument routinely used by proponents of managed or fixed exchange rates.

Foreign exchange rate fluctuations lead to exchange rate risk which is a potential gain or loss occasioned by movements in the exchange rate. In measuring fluctuations in foreign exchange rates, the following models can be applied: purchasing power parity theorem (PPP), the Mundell-Fleming model, the Balassa-Samuelson model or the International Fisher Effect (IFE) model.

Exchange rate refers to the absolute value of a country's currency in comparison with other currencies on equal footing. It is the weight of a country's currency in an international scale. It is usually the basis of international payment between countries (Madura, 2022).

2.1.2 Economic growth

Economic growth is an increase in the production of economic goods and services, compared from one period of time to another. It can be measured in nominal or real adjusted for inflation terms. Traditionally, aggregate economic growth is measured in terms of gross national product (GNP) or gross domestic product (GDP), although alternative metrics are sometimes used (Obi, 2021).

- 1) Economic growth is an increase in the production of goods and services in an economy.
- 2) Increases in capital goods, labor force, technology, and human capital can all contribute to economic growth.
- 3) Economic growth is commonly measured in terms of the increase in aggregated market value of additional goods and services produced, using estimates such as GDP.

In simplest terms, economic growth refers to an increase in aggregate production in an economy. Often, but not necessarily, aggregate gains in production correlate with increased average marginal productivity. That leads to an increase in incomes, inspiring consumers to open up their wallets and buy more, which means a higher material quality of life or standard of living (Nelson,2016).

In economics, growth is commonly modelled as a function of physical capital, human capital and technology. Simply put, increasing the quantity or quality of the working age population, the tools that they have to work with, and the recipes that they have available to combine capital, and raw materials, will lead to increased economic output. There are a few ways to generate economic growth. The first is an increase in the amount of physical capital goods in the economy (Harry,2019).

Adding capital to the economy tends to increase productivity of capital. Newer, better, and more tools mean that workers can produce more output per time period. For a simple example, a fisherman with a net will catch more fish per hour than a fisherman with a pointy stick. However two things are critical to this process. Someone in the economy must first engage in

some form of saving (sacrificing their current consumption) in order to free up the resources to create the new capital, and the new capital must be the right type, in the right place, at the right time for workers to actually use it productively (Eze, 2022).

A second method of producing economic growth is technological improvement. An example of this is the invention of gasoline fuel; prior to the discovery of the energy-generating power of gasoline, the economic value of petroleum was relatively low. The use of gasoline became a better and more productive method of transporting goods in process and distributing final goods more efficiently. Improved technology allows workers to produce more output with the same stock of capital goods, by combining them in novel ways that are more productive. Like capital growth, the rate of technical growth is highly dependent on the rate of savings and investment, since savings and investment are necessary to engage in research and development (Odekunle, 2018).

Another way to generate economic growth is to grow the labour force. All else equal, more workers generate more economic goods and services. During the 19th century, a portion of the robust U.S. economic growth was due to a high influx of cheap, productive immigrant. Like capital driven growth however, there are some key conditions to this process. Increasing the labor force also necessarily increases the amount of output that must be consumed in order to provide for the basic subsistence of the new workers, so the new workers need to be at least productive enough to offset this and not be net consumers (Islam,2019). Also just like additions to capital, it is important for the right type of workers to flow to the right jobs in the right places in combination with the right types of complementary capital goods in order to realize their productive potential (Judson, 2018).

The last method is increases in human capital. This means laborers become more skilled at their crafts, raising their productivity through skills training, trial and error, or simply more practice. Savings, investment, and specialization are the most consistent and easily controlled methods. Human capital in this context can also refer to social and institutional capital; behavioral tendencies toward higher social trust and reciprocity and political or economic innovations like improved protections for property rights are in effect types of human capital that can increase the productivity of the economy (Knowles, 2023).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) Theory

This theory was developed by Cassel in 1918. The theory is founded on the law of one price which posits that in the absence of transaction costs, identical goods should have the same price in different markets. The PPP theory, measures the purchasing power of one currency against another after taking into account their exchange rate. Under this theory, parity between the purchasing powers of different currencies establishes the rate of exchange between the two currencies. When the inflation rate differential between two currencies change, the exchange rate adjusts to correspond to the relative purchasing power of the currencies (Mailafia, 2018).

The relationship under this theory is derived from the basic idea that in the absence of trade restrictions, changes in the exchange rate mirror changes in the relative price levels in the two countries. At the same time under conditions of free trade, prices of similar commodities cannot differ between the two countries because arbitrageurs will take advantage of such conditions until price differences are eliminated. This leads to the law of one price which is to the effect that what is true of one commodity should be true of the economy as a whole (Oke, 2019). The price level in the two countries should be linked through the exchange rate and hence the notion that exchange rate changes are tied to inflation rate differences. If the theory doesn't hold, a conclusion is made that purchase parity doesn't exist between the two currencies (Madura, 2022).

2.3 Empirical Review

This section reviews the empirical literature on the subject matter. growth in both developed and developing economies. Gylfason and Schmidt (2023) examined the effect of devaluation on different countries' economy. They utilized a log-linear macro model of an open economy for a sample of ten countries, using different estimates of the key parameters of the model. Their results showed that devaluation was expansionary in eight of the ten countries investigated. Devaluation was found to be contractionary in two countries (United Kingdom and Brazil). Ndung'u (2023) estimated a six-variable VAR—money supply, domestic price level, exchange rate index, foreign price index, real output, and the rate of interest—in an attempt to explain the inflation movement in Kenya. He observed that the rate of inflation and exchange rate explained each other. A similar conclusion was also reached in the extended version of this study (Ndung'u, 2023).

Adebiyi and Dauda (2023) using error correction model argued on the contrary that trade liberalization promoted growth in the Nigerian industrial sector and stabilized the exchange rate market between 1970 and 2020. To them, there was a positive and significant relationship between index of industrial production and real export. A one per cent rise in real export increases the index of industrial production by 12.2 per cent. By implication, it means that the policy of deregulation impacted positively on export through exchange rate depreciation.

However, past studies also showed that exchange rate has no significant effect on economic growth performance. For example, Bosworth, Collins, and Yuchin (2023) provided evidence that in a large sample of industrial and developing countries, real exchange rate volatility hampers economic growth and reduces productivity growth.

Ubok-udom (2023) examined the issues surrounding the implementation of SAP in Nigeria, and drew up a conclusion that the peculiar features of Nigerian economy reduced the efficacy of currency depreciation in producing desirable effects. From the study of the relationship between exchange rate variation and growth of the domestic output in Nigeria (1971-2020); he expressed growth of domestic output as a linear function of variations in the average nominal exchange rate. He further used dummy variables to capture the periods of currency depreciation. The empirical result showed that all coefficients of the major explanatory variables have negative signs.

David, Umeh and Ameh (2023) also examined the effect of exchange rate fluctuations on Nigerian manufacturing industry. They employed multiple regression econometric tools which revealed a negative relationship between exchange rate volatility and manufacturing sector performance. Aghion et al. (2023) found a similar result, but they also showed that the negative effect of real exchange rate volatility on economic growth shrinks in countries with higher levels of financial development.

Barkoulas et al (2023) examined the impact of exchange rate fluctuation on the volume and variability of trade flows. They concluded that, exchange rate volatility discourages expansion of the volume of trade thereby reducing its benefits. Eichengreen and Leblang (2023) carried out their research in 12 countries over a period of 120 years and found strong inverse relationship between exchange rate stability and inflation. They concluded that the results of such estimations strongly depend on the time period and the sample.

Ogun (2023) studied on the impacts of real exchange rate on growth of non-oil export in Nigeria highlighted the effects of real exchange rate misalignment and volatility on the growth of non-oil exports. He employed the standard trade theory model of determinants of export growth and two different measures of real exchange misalignment, one of which entails deviation of the purchasing power parity (PPP), and the other which is model based estimation of equilibrium real exchange rate (ERER). He observed that irrespective of the alternative measures of misalignment employed, both real exchange misalignment and volatility adversely affected growth of Nigerian non-oil exports.

Arize, Osang, and Slottje (2023) found a significant negative relationship between increases in exchange rate volatility and inflation rate in developing countries. Servén (2023) showed that real exchange rate volatility negatively affects investment in a large panel of developing countries. This negative impact is significantly larger in countries with highly open economies and less developed financial systems. He also found evidence of threshold effects, whereby uncertainty only matters when it is relatively high.

A similar study, Eme and Johnson (2023) investigated the effect of exchange rate movements on inflation rate in Nigeria for the period 1996 –2021. The result revealed that there is no evidence of a strong direct relationship between changes in exchange rate and inflation rate. Rather, Nigeria inflation rate has been directly affected by monetary variables.

Empirical evidence has shown strong effect of short-run and long-run adverse effect of exchange rate swings on economic growth performance through the trade channel. The nature of the effect, however, runs in either position or negative direction.

According to IMF (2023) and European commission (2023) empirical evidence in favour of a systematic positive (or negative) effect of exchange rate stability on trade (and thereby growth) in small open economies has remained mixed. Bachetta and van Wincoop (2023) found based on a general equilibrium framework that exchange rate stability on trade.

In most empirical studies, the Gravity models have been used as frame work to quantify the impact of exchange rate stability on trade and growth, in particular in the context of monetary

union. Using panel estimations for more than 180 countries Edwards and Levy Yeyati (2022) found evidence that countries with more flexible exchange rate grow faster. Eichengreen and Lablang (2022) found strong negative relationship between exchange rate stability and growth for 12 countries over a period of 120 years. They conclude that the results of such estimations strongly depend on the time period and the sample Schnabel (2022) found robust evidence that exchange rate stability is associated with more growth in the EMU periphery. The evidence, according to him, is strong for Emerging Europe which has moved from an environment of high macro-economic instability to macro-economic stability during the observation period.

Martins and Muftau (2021) investigated the impact of exchange rate depreciation on balance of payment (BOP) in Nigeria over the period of 1961 – 2019. The analysis was based on a Multivariate Vector Error Correction framework. A long-term equilibrium relationship was found between exchange rate and other variables employed.

Akpan and Atan (2021) investigated the effect of exchange rate movement on economic growth in Nigeria. A Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) technique was employed. The estimation results suggest that there is no evidence of a strong direct relationship between changes in exchange rate and output growth. Rather, Nigeria's economic growth has been directly affected by monetary variables.

Oseni (2021) also analyzed the effect of exchange rate volatility and private sector consumption in Sub-Sahara Africa. The study employed generalized method of moments (GGM) dynamic panel regression econometric tools, which showed a negative relationship between exchange rate volatility and manufacturing sector performance.

Aliyu (2021) affirmed that appreciation of the exchange rate increases imports and reduces exports, while depreciation would expand export and discourage import. Also, depreciation of the exchange rate is likely to cause a shift from foreign goods to domestic goods. Thus, it leads to the diversion of income from importing countries to countries exporting through a shift in terms of trade, which tends to impact exporting and importing countries' economic growth.

It is important to mention the work of Odusola and Akinlo (2021) who examined the linkage among exchange rate, inflation and output in Nigeria. A structural VAR model was employed which captured the interactions between exchange rate and output. Evidence from the contemporaneous models showed a contractionary impact of the parallel exchange rate on output only in the short term. Prices, parallel exchange rate and lending rate were found to be important sources of perturbations in the official exchange rate. In addition, output and parallel exchange rate were significant determinants of inflation dynamics in Nigeria. The authors concluded by suggesting more concerted efforts by the Central Bank towards taming the parallel exchange rate behavior and formulating monetary policies that enhance income growth. Largely the findings were informative.

Morley (2021) analyzed the effect of real exchange rates on output for twenty eight developing countries that have devalued their currencies using a regression framework. After the introduction of controls for factors that could simultaneously induce devaluation and reduce output including terms of trade, import growth, the money supply, and the fiscal balance, he

discovered that depreciation of the level of the real exchange rate reduced the output.

Mahonnye & Tenda (2019) examined the exchange rate impact on output and inflation. This research looked at the inflationary effect of currency devaluation and its contractionary effect on real output growth in Zimbabwe. The study used quarterly data from 1990 – 2006 and used the Johansen co-integration regression test and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The study found that in both the short run and long run, fluctuations in the real exchange rates are significant on real output growth and expansion.

Asher (2018) examined the impact of exchange rate fluctuation on the Nigeria economic growth for period of 1980 –2010. The result showed that real exchange rate has a positive effect on the economic growth. In a similar study, Akpan (2018) investigated foreign exchange market and economic growth in an emerging petroleum based economy from 1970-2003 in Nigeria. He found that positive relationship exists between exchange rate and economic growth.

Obansa, Okoroafor, Aluko and Millicent (2018) also examined the relationship between exchange rate and economic growth in Nigeria between 1970 –2010. The result indicated that exchange rate has a strong impact on economic growth. They concluded that exchange rate liberalization was good to Nigerian economy as it promote economic growth. Azeez, Kolapo and Ajayi (2018) also investigated the effect of exchange rate volatility on macroeconomic performance in Nigeria from 1986 –2016. They discovered that exchange rate is positive related to Gross Domestic Product. Adebisi and Dauda (2018) using error correction model argued on the contrary that trade liberalization promoted growth in the Nigerian industrial sector and stabilized the exchange rate market between 1980 and 2016. To them, there was a positive and significant relationship between index of industrial production and real export. A one per cent rise in real export increases the index of industrial production by 12.2 per cent. By implication, it means that the policy of deregulation impacted positively on export through exchange rate depreciation.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a quantitative type of research in which the secondary data is used. The use of secondary method was chosen for this study because it is considered to be the most appropriate method for the needed information. The secondary data for the paper was sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical bulletin, and National Bureau of statistics, 2024. There are two variables: dependent and independent variables. The dependent variable is Gross Domestic Product Growth rate (GDPGR), while the independent variables are; exchange rate (EXR), inflation rate (INF), foreign direct investment (FDI), trade openness (TRD) and interest rate (IR). This study examined the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variable. The Estimation technique and tools of analysis include; the Autoregressive Distributed Lag model (ARDL), multiple linear regression model, unit root test, descriptive statistics, Granger causality test, among others.

Estimation Techniques

Autoregressive Distributed lag (ARDL)

The study employed Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL). Due to the advantages associated with it. First, the ARDL model is the more statistically significant approach to determining the co-integration relationship in small samples (Ghalak and Siddiki, 2001), while the Johansen co-integration technique requires large data samples for validity. Second, the Johansen approach of co-integration requires all of the regressors to be integrated of the same order, while the ARDL approach can be applied whether the regressors are I (1) and I (0). This means that the ARDL approach avoids the pre-testing problems associated with standard co-integration, which requires that the variables be already classified into I (1) or I (0) Pesaran et al, (2001).

Model Specification

The ARDL model is specified as:

$$\Delta GDPGR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Delta GDPGR_{t-i} + \beta_2 \Delta FDI_{t-i} + \beta_3 \Delta EXR_{t-i} + \beta_4 \Delta TRD_{t-i} + \beta_5 \Delta INF_{t-i} + \beta_6 \Delta IR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p GDPGR + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_9 \Delta FDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_{10} \Delta EXR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_{11} \Delta TRD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_{12} \Delta INF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_{13} \Delta IR_{t-i} + ECM + \mu_t$$

Where:

Δ = the Difference Operator

GDPGR= Gross Domestic Product Growth rate

EXR = Exchange rate

INF = Inflation rate

FDI = Foreign Direct Investment

IR=Interest Rate

TRD= Trade Openness

ECM=Error Correction Mechanism

U=Error Term

β_1 =Intercept of the model

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_{14}$ = Partial Slopes of the Linear regression model

Unit Root Test: It is used to test for the stationarity of the time series data. This involves testing of the order of integration of the individual time series under consideration. These tests are initially performed at levels and then in first difference form. In addition, the unit root test will be carried out using the Augmented Dickey Fuller test (ADF). The results of the unit root

tests will also show if the series are stationary in first differences I (1) or series in levels have unit root—I (0) or both.

Granger-Causality Test: It is used to test for the long run relationship between the variables. And a long run relationship is found on these variables in which we will study. According to Granger (1969), Y is said to “Granger-cause” X if and only if X is better predicted by using the past values of Y than by not doing so with the past values of X being used in either case.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics test provides a brief explanation of the coefficients that summarizes the data set used in the study. In a tabular form, it represents the entire population of the study. Table 4.1 below presents the summary statistics of the individual variables under consideration which include Gross Domestic Product growth rate, (GDPGR), inflation rate (INF), interest rate (IR), Foreign direct investment (FDI), Trade openness (TRD) and Exchange rate (EXR). Each variable of interest contained 45 observations. The table shows that Foreign direct investment (FDI) has the highest mean and median values closely followed by the mean and median scores of Exchange rate (EXR), inflation rate (INF), interest rate (IR) and GDP growth rate while trade openness (TRD) recorded the lowest mean and median values.

Similarly, the maximum values, revealed that Foreign direct investment (FDI) has the highest maximum value closely followed by the maximum scores of Exchange rate (EXR), inflation rate (INF), interest rate (IR) and GDP growth rate while trade openness (TRD) recorded the lowest maximum value. Next is the minimum score, findings showed that foreign direct investment has the largest minimum value, while GDP growth rate recorded the lowest minimum value. The kurtosis values revealed that all the variables of interest appeared to be Leptokurtic in nature as the kurtosis values are greater than three (3). In addition, the probability of Jarque-Bera test shows that these variables (GDPGR, EXR, FDI, TRD and INF) are normally distributed, while IR is not normally distributed. The skewness test shows that inflation rate (INF), interest rate (IR), Foreign direct investment (FDI), Trade openness (TRD) and Exchange rate (EXR) are positively skewed, while Gross Domestic Product growth rate, (GDPGR) was negatively skewed.

Table 4.1: Descriptive statistics of all variables

	GDPGR	FDI	EXR	TRD	INF	IR
Mean	2.771518	6193044.	150.3558	0.330133	19.50422	17.17933
Median	3.265201	259250.6	118.5700	0.330595	13.67000	17.50000
Maximum	15.32916	1.09E+08	886.2900	0.818159	72.84000	29.80000
Minimum	-13.12790	27240.80	0.550000	0.091359	1.030000	7.500000
Std. Dev.	5.615117	21685932	210.9022	0.157233	16.49487	4.870633
Skewness	-0.959759	4.273472	2.131773	0.887985	1.736667	0.195859
Kurtosis	4.587787	19.75219	6.893111	4.347097	5.180173	3.158684
Jarque-Bera	11.63554	663.1614	62.50150	9.316388	31.53226	0.334921
Probability	0.002974	0.000000	0.000000	0.009484	0.000000	0.845810

Sum	124.7183	2.79E+08	6766.010	14.85600	877.6900	773.0700
Sum Sq. Dev.	1387.300	2.07E+16	1957109.	1.087776	11971.55	1043.815
Observations	45	45	45	45	45	45

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025 (Eviews-12)

Where:

GDPGR= Gross Domestic Product Growth rate

EXR = Exchange rate

INF = Inflation rate

FDI = Foreign Direct Investment

IR=Interest Rate

TRD= Trade Openness

Unit Root Tests

Table 4.2 shows the unit root test results of the variables examined in this study using Augmented Dickey Fuller techniques. The aim of the unit root test is to ascertain the stationarity properties of the variables of interest which guide in choosing the appropriate technique of analysis to avoid a misleading or spurious regression result.

Table 4.2: ADF Unit root test Results on Variables in specified model

Variable	ADF-Statistic	Critical value 1%	Critical value 5%	Critical value 10%	Oder of Integration	Interpretation
GDPGR	-2.363668	-2.619851	-1.948686	-1.612036	I(0)	Stationary at level
FDI	4.469946	-2.632688	-1.950687	-1.611059	I(0)	Stationary at level
EXR	6.962172	-2.618579	-1.948495	-1.612135	I(0)	Stationary at level
TRD	-7.972275	-2.621185	-1.948886	-1.611932	I (1)	Stationary at 1 st difference
INF	-6.557798	-2.621185	-1.948886	-1.611932	I (1)	Stationary at 1 st difference
IR	-6.493938	-2.621185	-1.948886	-1.611932	I (1)	Stationary at 1 st difference

Source: Author’s Computation (2025) Using E-views 12

Table 4.2 above shows the summary of the Augmented Dickey Unit root test result. The table indicates that Gross Domestic Product growth rate, foreign direct investment and exchange rate were stationary at level, while trade openness, Inflation Rate, and Interest rate are Stationary at first difference.

Table 4.3: ARDL Long Run Form and Bounds Test

ARDL Long Run Form and Bounds Test	
Dependent Variable: D(GDPGR)	
Selected Model: ARDL(1, 0, 0, 0, 3, 0)	
Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend	
Date: 06/29/25 Time: 00:55	

Sample: 1980 2024				
Included observations: 42				
Conditional Error Correction Regression				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-2.965416	2.759474	-1.074631	0.2906
GDPGR(-1)*	-0.815508	0.139499	-5.845988	0.0000
FDI**	5.66E-08	4.91E-08	1.152933	0.2575
EXR**	-0.004019	0.005750	-0.698931	0.4896
TRD**	6.118104	4.925589	1.242106	0.2232
INF(-1)	-0.155097	0.054033	-2.870420	0.0072
IR**	0.410611	0.159159	2.579879	0.0147
D(INF)	-0.105545	0.038083	-2.771412	0.0092
D(INF(-1))	0.048225	0.043335	1.112838	0.2741
D(INF(-2))	0.095487	0.039036	2.446125	0.0201
* p-value incompatible with t-Bounds distribution.				
** Variable interpreted as $Z = Z(-1) + D(Z)$.				
Levels Equation				
Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FDI	6.94E-08	5.95E-08	2.167564	0.0316
EXR	-0.004928	0.006999	-0.704062	0.4865
TRD	7.502196	5.835188	2.285682	0.0278
INF	-0.190184	0.061359	-3.099524	0.0040
IR	0.503503	0.183530	2.743442	0.0099
C	-3.636279	3.331267	-1.091560	0.2832
EC = GDPGR - (0.0000*FDI -0.0049*EXR + 7.5022*TRD -0.1902*INF + 0.5035*IR - 3.6363)				
F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
			Asymptotic: n=1000	
F-statistic	5.068656	10%	2.08	3
K	5	5%	2.39	3.38
		2.5%	2.7	3.73
		1%	3.06	4.15
Actual Sample Size	42		Finite Sample: n=45	
		10%	2.276	3.297
		5%	2.694	3.829
		1%	3.674	5.019
			Finite Sample: n=40	
		10%	2.306	3.353
		5%	2.734	3.92
		1%	3.657	5.256

Source: Author's Computation, 2025 (Eviews-12)

To ascertain if there is a long run cointegrating relationship between the dependent and independent variables, we need to conduct ARDL Bounds Test. The above table 4.3 shows that there is a long run cointegrating relationship between the dependent and independent variables, this decision is based on the fact that the Calculated F-statistic (5.068656) is greater than the critical values for the upper and lower bound at all level of significance. Therefore, it can be inferred that a long run cointegrating relationship exists between the dependent variable (GDP Growth rate) and the independent variables (FDI, EXR, TRD, INF, IR).

In the long run, ARDL estimation revealed that foreign direct investment, interest rate, and trade openness had a positive and significant impact on the economic growth in Nigeria, while exchange rate and inflation rate impacted negatively and insignificantly on the economic growth in Nigeria during the period under review.

Table 4.4: ARDL Short Run Estimation

Dependent Variable: GDPGR				
Method: ARDL				
Date: 06/29/25 Time: 00:52				
Sample (adjusted): 1983 2024				
Included observations: 42 after adjustments				
Maximum dependent lags: 4 (Automatic selection)				
Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)				
Dynamic regressors (4 lags, automatic): FDI EXR TRD INF IR				
Fixed regressors: C				
Number of models evaluated: 12500				
Selected Model: ARDL(1, 0, 0, 0, 3, 0)				
Note: final equation sample is larger than selection sample				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
GDPGR(-1)	0.184492	0.139499	1.322532	0.1954
FDI	5.66E-08	4.91E-08	2.152933	0.0275
EXR	-0.004019	0.005750	-0.698931	0.4896
TRD	6.118104	4.925589	1.242106	0.2232
INF	-0.105545	0.038083	-2.771412	0.0092
INF(-1)	-0.001327	0.049890	-0.026594	0.9789
INF(-2)	0.047262	0.047909	0.986506	0.3313
INF(-3)	-0.095487	0.039036	-2.446125	0.0201
IR	0.410611	0.159159	2.579879	0.0147
C	-2.965416	2.759474	-1.074631	0.2906
R-squared	0.554617	Mean dependent var		3.733424
Adjusted R-squared	0.429353	S.D. dependent var		4.365025
S.E. of regression	3.297392	Akaike info criterion		5.428397
Sum squared resid	347.9294	Schwarz criterion		5.842128
Log likelihood	-103.9963	Hannan-Quinn criter.		5.580046
F-statistic	4.427584	Durbin-Watson stat		2.053991
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000802			
*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model				

Source: Author's Computation, 2025 (Eviews-12)

Similarly, the ARDL short run result in table 4.4 reveals that foreign direct investment, interest rate, and trade openness had a positive and significant impact on the economic growth in Nigeria, while exchange rate and inflation rate had negative and insignificant impact on the economic growth in Nigeria during the period under review.

Also, the coefficient of determination is about 0.55, which implies that about 55 percent of the variation in GDP growth rate is explained by variations in all the independent variables, while the remaining 45% is unexplained which implies the estimated model has a good fit. The F-statistic probability value (0.0008) is also significant which implies that all the independent variables are jointly statistically significant. Finally, the DW statistic value (2.05) shows an absence of autocorrelation in the model. This result is reliable for planning, forecasting, predication and decision making.

Table 4.5: ARDL Error Correction Regression

ARDL Error Correction Regression				
Dependent Variable: D(GDPGR)				
Selected Model: ARDL(1, 0, 0, 0, 3, 0)				
Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend				
Date: 06/29/25 Time: 01:04				
Sample: 1980 2024				
Included observations: 42				
ECM Regression				
Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(INF)	-0.105545	0.031531	-3.347290	0.0021
D(INF(-1))	0.048225	0.029123	1.655929	0.1075
D(INF(-2))	0.095487	0.031819	3.000937	0.0052
CointEq(-1)*	-0.815508	0.125637	-6.491009	0.0000
R-squared	0.587860	Mean dependent var		0.287586
Adjusted R-squared	0.555323	S.D. dependent var		4.537652
S.E. of regression	3.025894	Akaike info criterion		5.142683
Sum squared resid	347.9294	Schwarz criterion		5.308176
Log likelihood	-103.9963	Hannan-Quinn criter.		5.203343
Durbin-Watson stat	2.053991			
* p-value incompatible with t-Bounds distribution.				
F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	5.068656	10%	2.08	3
K	5	5%	2.39	3.38
		2.5%	2.7	3.73
		1%	3.06	4.15

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025 (Eviews-12)

Table 4.5 shows that the lagged coefficient of the Error Correction term (ECT(-1)) i.e, CointEq(-1)* is negative, less than one and statistically significant at 5% as captured by a probability value of 0.0000. The coefficient of the ECT(-1) implies that once there is disequilibrium in the system or economy, it will take an average of 81% to restore the long

run relationship between the dependent variable (GDPGR) and independent variables (FDI, EXR, TRD, IR and INF). Table 4.5 further indicates that the coefficient of determination is about 0.59, this suggests that 59 percent of the fluctuations in GDPGR can be accounted for by variations in all the independent variables, while 41 percent of the unaccounted variations were captured by the error term. It implies that the estimated model has a good fit. Finally, the DW statistic (D-W=2.05), approximately two (2) shows an absence of autocorrelation in the model.

Table 4.6: Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests			
Date: 06/29/25 Time: 01:06			
Sample: 1980 2024			
Lags: 2			
Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
FDI does not Granger Cause GDPGR	43	0.16958	0.8447
GDPGR does not Granger Cause FDI		0.08916	0.9149
EXR does not Granger Cause GDPGR	43	0.03145	0.9691
GDPGR does not Granger Cause EXR		1.49115	0.2380
TRD does not Granger Cause GDPGR	43	0.45810	0.6359
GDPGR does not Granger Cause TRD		1.46568	0.2437
INF does not Granger Cause GDPGR	43	0.20317	0.8170
GDPGR does not Granger Cause INF		0.20267	0.8174
IR does not Granger Cause GDPGR	43	1.13111	0.3333
GDPGR does not Granger Cause IR		5.42563	0.0085
EXR does not Granger Cause FDI	43	8.39213	0.0010
FDI does not Granger Cause EXR		1.07056	0.3529
TRD does not Granger Cause FDI	43	6.11387	0.0050
FDI does not Granger Cause TRD		0.49785	0.6117
INF does not Granger Cause FDI	43	0.03243	0.9681
FDI does not Granger Cause INF		0.06466	0.9375
IR does not Granger Cause FDI	43	0.20920	0.8122
FDI does not Granger Cause IR		0.45833	0.6358
TRD does not Granger Cause EXR	43	3.97627	0.0270
EXR does not Granger Cause TRD		0.18130	0.8349
INF does not Granger Cause EXR	43	0.06280	0.9392
EXR does not Granger Cause INF		0.06089	0.9410
IR does not Granger Cause EXR	43	0.48963	0.6167
EXR does not Granger Cause IR		0.75693	0.4760
INF does not Granger Cause TRD	43	0.02475	0.9756
TRD does not Granger Cause INF		0.13256	0.8763
IR does not Granger Cause TRD	43	1.41800	0.2547
TRD does not Granger Cause IR		0.11398	0.8926
IR does not Granger Cause INF	43	0.20930	0.8121
INF does not Granger Cause IR		3.67160	0.0348

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025 (Eviews-12)

Table 4.6 presents the Granger causality test result. The results show that unidirectional relationship runs between interest rate and gross domestic product growth rate, while no

causality runs between the following variables; exchange rate and GDP growth rate, inflation rate and GDP growth rate, foreign direct investment and GDP growth rate, as well as trade openness and GDP growth rate in other words, Exchange rate does not Granger Cause GDP, also GDP does not Granger Cause Exchange rate.

Post Estimation

Table 4.7: Diagnostic Analysis

Type	Diagnostic Test	F-stat.	Probability
Breusch-Godfrey LM Test	Serial Correlation	0.091562	0.9136
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Test	Heteroskedasticity	0.696691	0.7613
Ramsey RESET Test	Specification	0.172763	0.6886
Jarque-Bera Test	Normality	2.725007	0.256019

Source: Author's computation using E-Views 12

The reliability of the regression results from our dynamic model was assessed through various diagnostic checks, the outcomes of which are presented in Table 4.7. The tests are: Using the Breusch-Godfrey Test to check for serial correlation and the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Test to check for heteroskedasticity, validation of model specification via the Ramsey RESET Test, and evaluation of normality using the Jarque-Bera Test were conducted to ensure the robustness of the regression results. The F-stats and probabilities obtained reflect positivity as they all suggest the rejection of null hypothesis for each category of diagnostic tests. Explicatively, the serial correlation test result shows the absence of serial correlation as an econometric problem, BPG Test shows that the model is not characterized by homoskedasticity, Ramsey REST Test result justifies the model specification's goodness as previously established and given that the probability value of each variable is greater than 0.05 or 5%, the Jarque-Bera test indicates that the variables are regularly distributed.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The study examined the impact of exchange rate on the economic growth in Nigeria (1980-2024). Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) was employed to test for the stationarity of the variables under study. The result of the unit root test revealed that Gross Domestic Product growth rate, foreign direct investment and exchange rate were stationary at level, while trade openness, Inflation Rate, and Interest rate are Stationary at first difference.

The study also conducted ARDL estimation, the Bounds Test shows that there is a long run cointegrating relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Also, both the short run and long run ARDL estimations revealed that foreign direct investment, interest rate, and trade openness had a positive and significant impact on the economic growth in Nigeria, while exchange rate and inflation rate impacted negatively and significantly on the economic growth in Nigeria during the period under review.

The Granger causality test show that unidirectional relationship runs between interest rate and gross domestic product growth rate, while no causality runs between the following variables; exchange rate and GDP growth rate, inflation rate and GDP growth rate, foreign direct

investment and GDP growth rate, as well as trade openness and GDP growth rate. In other words, Exchange rate does not Granger Cause GDP, also GDP does not Granger Cause Exchange rate. Empirically, findings revealed that foreign direct investment, trade openness, exchange rate, inflation rate and interest rate has proven to be among the key economic indicators as well as a catalyst of Economic growth in Nigeria.

Policy Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The Central Bank of Nigeria and other relevant stakeholders should embark on appropriate monetary policy aimed at addressing the challenges of high inflation rate as this can boost consumers' purchasing power.
- ii. The Central Bank of Nigeria, policy makers and other relevant stakeholders should embark on policies aimed at addressing the exchange rate fluctuation as this can boost domestic production which will likely lead to economic growth in Nigeria.
- iii. The Central Bank of Nigeria and other relevant authorities should adopt and implement the appropriate monetary and fiscal policies aimed at controlling high interest rate. This will boost investors' confidence and attract more investors into the Country.
- iv. The federal and state Government as well as other relevant stakeholders should embark on policies aimed at encouraging foreign direct investment as such policies can boost both domestic and foreign trade which will likely lead to economic growth in Nigeria.
- v. The Central Bank of Nigeria, policy makers and other key stakeholders should initiate measures geared towards export promotion and import substitution as such measures can boost trade openness in Nigeria.

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